

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids from the Stand-
point of Smoluchowski's Theory. Part III.
Coagulation of Arsenious Sulphide
Sol by Sulphuric Acid Solutions.**

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It was found in Part II (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 337) that in the slow coagulations of the arsenious sulphide sol, using dilute sulphuric acid solutions, the diminution of β , the Smoluchowski's constant occurred mainly during the early stages of coagulation. As this conclusion is contrary to the results of some workers (*loc. cit.*) it has been examined here in more detail.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental procedure, the method of preparing the sol, of measuring (a) and ($a-x$), the colloid content at the beginning, and at a time t after the start of coagulation respectively, were the same as in Part II. The results in Tables I—III and in Fig. 1 refer to coagulations at 18° and 60° for different colloids and electrolyte concentrations. β , and k the bimolecular constant, were calculated from $\beta = 1/t \left[\sqrt{\frac{n_0}{n_1}} - 1 \right]$ and $k = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{x}{(a-x)}$ respectively.

The results under β_{T_1}/β_{T_2} in tables relate the observed influence of temperature on β , with that deduced from Smoluchowski's theory (*vide infra*). Curves in Fig. 2 indicate the variation of β during coagulation in different experiments deduced from data in the tables and Fig. 1.

Discussion.

The results show that the rate of coagulation is increased by increasing the temperature. This is contrary to the observations of Linder and Picton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1906) on the coagulation of the arsenious sulphide sol by dilute sulphuric acid at 13° and

FIG. 1.

Curves c, c' of Table I.

b, b' II.

a, a' III.

70°. They found that the coagulating concentration was greater at the higher temperature. No definite details as regards the colloid and coagulator concentration as used by them are available. It would appear, however, that the result is not above criticism, since the degree of coagulation was measured by an indirect turbidity method.

In agreement with previous results the coagulation—time curves in Fig. 1 show that the process cannot be regarded as autocatalytic, although no special precautions were taken to prevent the formation of any coagulation nuclei in the system by stirring etc.

These results also show that the influence of temperature in increasing the rate of coagulation depends on the colloid concentration (*cf.* curves, *a, a'* and *c, c'*, Fig. 1) when that of the coagulator is constant. That the last quantity is also a determinant of the temperature influence on coagulation is apparent from curves, *b, b'*, Fig. 1. This departs markedly from those, characteristic of molecular chemical reactions, and also from the simple mechanism of the coagulation process contemplated in Smoluchowski's theory (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129). According to this theory β at two temperatures T_1 , and T_2 , is given by $\frac{4}{3} \frac{RT_1}{N_0} \cdot \frac{\eta_0}{\eta_1}$ and $\frac{4}{3} \frac{RT_2}{N_0} \cdot \frac{\eta_0}{\eta_2}$, where η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the medium corresponding to T_1 and T_2 , respectively. It must be pointed out here, that in deriving the above equation it has been tacitly assumed that temperature has no influence on a factor ϵ which denotes the probability of coalescence between two colloid particles in the coagulating sol.

It is well known that different coagulators do not alter the coagulation rate to approximately the same extent, or even always in the same direction, as the temperature is increased. The above equation, however, implies that the temperature coefficient of β depends only on the viscosity and the temperature of the medium, and is therefore independent of the nature both of the coagulator and of the colloid. The observed departure from Smoluchowski's theory, as regarding the temperature influence can be explained therefore by considering ϵ , as determined mainly by the ionic adsorption, and therefore a function of the nature of the colloid and of the coagulator; ϵ is therefore variable with temperature (*cf.* Part I. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11). The results under k and β show that contrary to the requirements of Smoluchowski's theory, and in agreement with general results on slow coagulation, these quantities diminish during coagulation.

The diminution of β during coagulation would appear to be mainly due to diminution of ϵ . As there is not much information in the literature on this point, it is interesting to see that the time variation of β in all the coagulations studied is characterized by regular curves, *A, A', B, B', C, C'*, in Fig. 2. It is seen from these data and in agreement with previous results (Part II. *loc. cit.*) that the diminution of β is appreciably greater during the earlier stages of coagulation than later.

FIG. 2.

Curves C, C', C₁ & C'₁ relate β with t and $1/t$ [curves c, c' Fig. 1].

B, B', B₁ & B'₁ [b, b'].

A, A', A₁ & A'₁ [a, a'].

TABLE I.

0.125 N/H₂SO₄. 1 c.c. of K₂Cr₂O₇ = 0.001688 g. As₂S₃.
 Time in Titre in c.c. dichromate (a-x) g. As₂S₃ per litre.

min.	solution.		18°		60°		18°		60°	
	18°	60°	18°	60°	18°	60°	obs.	cal.	18°	60°
0	7.19	..	.605	..	.075	..	..	..	..	..
1	6.22	6.17	.519	.523	.075	.079	1.05	..	1.57	.166
2.5	6.10	6.10	.513	.513	.084	.084	1.00	..	.072	.072
5	..	6.05	..	.509	..	.018	..	2.62	..	..
10	6.01	5.96	.506	.502	.009	.010	1.11	..	.019	.088
										.020

Initial colloid conc. = 1.21 g. As₂S₃ per litre.
 β_{T_1}/β_{T_2}

TABLE II.

0.204 N/H₂SO₄. 1 c.c. of K₂Cr₂O₇ = 0.001525 g. As₂S₃.
 Initial colloid conc. = 1.16 g. As₂S₃ per litre.

	14°		60°		14°		60°			
	14°	60°	14°	60°	14°	60°	14°	60°		
0	7.60	..	.580	..	.201	.268	1.33	..	..	..
1	5.27	4.72	.402	.360	.086	.131	1.42	..	4.43	.611
2.5	5.15	4.31	.393	.329	..	..	..	2.82	.190	.305
5	5.05	4.28	.385	.323	.045	.068	1.51	..	.101	.159
10	4.98	4.02	.380	.307	.023	.037	1.60	..	.053	.089
15	4.89	..	.373	..	.013	..	..	..	.037	..

TABLE III.

0.125 N/H₂SO₄. 1 c.c. of K₂Cr₂O₇ = 0.001688 g. As₂S₃.
 Initial colloid conc. = 0.48 g. As₂S₃ per litre.

	18°		60°		18°		60°			
	18°	60°	18°	60°	18°	60°	18°	60°		
0	2.85	..	.240	..	.112	.161	1.44	..	..	..
1	2.31	2.12	.194	.178	.059	.074	1.28	..	.237	.348
2.5	2.21	2.03	.186	.171	..	..	..	2.62	.116	.161
5	2.17	..	.183	..	.029	..	..	..	.062	..
10	2.12	1.84	.178	.155	.016	.024	1.50	..	.085	.055

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